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Title:

Analysis of electric current density in carbon fiber reinforced plastic laminated plates with angled plies

Authors:

Takuya Yamane

Graduate Student of Tokyo Institute of Technology
Department of Mechanical Sciences and Engineering
Tokyo Institute of Technology

2-12-1 (i1-58), Ookayama, Meguro, Tokyo 1528550 Japan

Tel/Fax +81 03-5734-3178

E-mail: tyamane@ginza.mes.titech.ac.jp

and

Akira Todoroki* (Corresponding author)

Department of Mechanical Sciences and Engineering
Tokyo Institute of Technology

2-12-1 (i1-58), Ookayama, Meguro, Tokyo 1528550 Japan

Tel/Fax +81 03-5734-3178

E-mail: atodorok@ginza.mes.titech.ac.jp

Tokyo Institute of Technology

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1.Introduction

Laminated carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites are widely used in aerospace and automobile construction. Laminated CFRP plates have an anisotropic electric conductivity, in that the electric current density distribution depends on the stacking sequence of the CFRP laminated plate when an electric current is applied. Because the plies of a CFRP laminated plate have anisotropic conductivity, the electric current density distribution forms in a complicated configuration. Highly toughened CFRP laminates used for aircraft structures have resin rich layers to increase their delamination toughness. The resin rich layer has extremely low electrical conductivity in the through-thickness direction [1]. When an aircraft structure is hit by a lightning strike, the electric current flow is quite difficult to predict. Durability against lightning strikes is currently assessed experimentally and lightning strike damage to laminated CFRP plates has been widely studied [1-6]. To help reduce the costs of such experiments, new analysis methods for the electric current density distribution are required. Accurate electrical current analysis of laminated CFRP plates may also allow damage monitoring of laminated CFRP plates based on changes in electrical resistance [7-21]. However, it remains difficult to calculate the electric current distribution in each ply using a finite element method (FEM) or a finite difference method (FDM) because of the high computational cost: a large number of meshes are indispensable for the analysis.

A new analysis method has been proposed to calculate the electric current density of a laminated CFRP beam using an orthotropic electric potential function [19-21]. This method assumes that the laminated CFRP beam is electrically orthotropic, and provides the electric current density of each ply using an orthotropic electric potential function. Because an analytical function is used, the calculation costs of this method are much lower than those of the FEM or FDM. The method has been applied to unidirectional beams, plates and cross-ply laminated beams and shown good agreement with other computational methods and

experimental results [22][23]. Previous papers [22][23] have shown that toughened CFRP plates with resin rich layers can be treated as homogeneous orthotropic materials using this method.

Actual laminated CFRP structures typically feature angled ply structures, including $\pm 45^\circ$ -plies, and occasionally 0° -plies and 90° -plies. Real laminated CFRP plates that feature angled plies do not have an orthotropic electric conductivity. This prevents use of the analytical function to calculate the electric current density of laminated CFRP plates that feature angle plies.

In the present study, a new approximation method is proposed to calculate electric current density in typical laminated CFRP plates that contains angle plies. The new method is applied to a unidirectional CFRP plate, and two types of quasi-isotropic laminates comprising 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° plies. The results calculated by this method are compared with numerical computational methods and with experimental results to confirm the validity of the new method.

2. Orthotropic electric potential function analysis

2.1 Orthotropic electric potential function analysis for unidirectional CFRP [19]

First, the orthotropic electric potential function analysis of a unidirectional CFRP is briefly explained. A laminated unidirectional CFRP is assumed to be a homogeneous orthotropic electric conductive material. Let the electric current flow direction be x , the transverse direction y , and the through-thickness direction z . Generally, the x -axis is equal to the fiber or transverse direction because the analysis is limited to the orthotropic conductivity. The electric conductivities in the x -, y - and z -directions are σ_x , σ_y and σ_z respectively. The electric current density in each direction can be expressed as follows,

$$i_x = -\sigma_x \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x}, \quad i_y = -\sigma_y \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y}, \quad i_z = -\sigma_z \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z}. \quad (1)$$

The continuity of electric current gives the following equation,

$$\sigma_x \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} + \sigma_y \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial y^2} + \sigma_z \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial z^2} = 0. \quad (2)$$

Affine transformations are adopted as follows,

$$\xi = \frac{x}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}}, \quad \eta = \frac{y}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}}, \quad \zeta = \frac{z}{\sqrt{\sigma_z}}. \quad (3)$$

Using the affine transformation, equation (2) becomes,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \xi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \eta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \zeta^2} = 0. \quad (4)$$

This is a Laplace equation in isotropic media. This means that the electric current in the orthotropic material can be regarded as an ideal flow in isotropic media using equation (3). This enables potential functions of perfect flow to be used for analysis of electric current. For analysis of the electric current, potential functions of a source and a sink are used to express the electric current source and a ground.

Let us consider the case shown in Figure 1. The electric current source is located at the point $(a_{1x}, a_{1y}, 0)$. The ground is located at the point $(a_{2x}, a_{2y}, 0)$. The total electric current is I . The potential functions shown in Figure 1 become a superposition of the source ϕ_{source} and the sink ϕ_{sink} . Each potential can be expressed as follows,

$$\phi_{\text{source}} = \frac{I}{2\pi\sqrt{\sigma_x\sigma_y\sigma_z}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{(x-a_{1x})^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y-a_{1y})^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}}, \quad (5)$$

$$\phi_{\text{sink}} = -\frac{I}{2\pi\sqrt{\sigma_x\sigma_y\sigma_z}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{(x-a_{2x})^2}{\sigma_x} + \frac{(y-a_{2y})^2}{\sigma_y} + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}}. \quad (6)$$

The actual electric potential function is the sum of the equations (5) and (6). The orthotropic electric potential functions are described in reference [19].

For damage monitoring using changes in electrical resistance, the electrodes are not a

single point, but rectangular as shown in Figure 2. To obtain the electric potential of finite area electrodes, the electric potential function is integrated over the electrode area as shown in the equation (7).

$$\phi = \frac{1}{(a_{1y2} - a_{1y1})(a_{1x2} - a_{1x1})} \int_{a_{1y1}}^{a_{1y2}} \int_{a_{1x1}}^{a_{1x2}} \phi_{\text{source}} da_{1x} da_{1y} + \frac{1}{(a_{2y2} - a_{2y1})(a_{2x2} - a_{2x1})} \int_{a_{2y1}}^{a_{2y2}} \int_{a_{2x1}}^{a_{2x2}} \phi_{\text{sink}} da_{2x} da_{2y} \quad (7)$$

For a unidirectional CFRP laminate, electric conductivities in the fiber direction, transverse direction and through-thickness direction are σ_0 , σ_{90} and σ_t . When an electrical current is input in the fiber direction, the conductivities of σ_0 , σ_{90} and σ_t are substituted into σ_x , σ_y and σ_z respectively. Equation (1) gives the electric current density [22]. The whole formula of the equation (7) is shown in Appendix.

2.2 Analysis of finite plate using mirror image method [20]

The electric potential function shown in the equation (7) is applicable for an infinite body. For a finite plate, the electric potential function can be modified using mirror images. The mirror image method for a plate is shown in Figure 3. The total number of mirror images required for the exact analysis is evaluated using the electric current that flows in the finite plate region [20].

2.3 Modified analysis using equivalent conductivity for cross-ply laminated plate

When an electric current source and a ground are located on the top surface of a laminated CFRP plate, the electric potential difference has its maximum value at the surface, and decreases with increasing distance from the surface. The decrease of the electric potential difference arises from the low electrical conductivity in the through-thickness direction. The distribution of the electrical potential depends on the ratio of electrical conductivity between σ_x and σ_z . For cross-ply laminates, σ_x gives the exact distribution of the electric potential, and the electric potential difference is not equal to σ_0 or σ_{90} . In our previous study, the electric

potential distribution was obtained using an equivalent conductivity σ_e . The detail for a beam composite is shown in reference [21]. The modified process used two directions, and is described briefly as follows.

(1) Using a unidirectional 0° -ply laminate, the electric potential differences ($\partial\phi/\partial x$ and $\partial\phi/\partial y$) at one point $(x, y) = (-a_{1x}, a_{1x})$ are calculated using the orthotropic electric potential function.

Note that the point should not be on the coordinate axis ($x=0$ and $y=0$).

(2) Normalized contribution functions $F_x(\alpha)$ and $F_y(\alpha)$ are obtained from the calculated electric potential difference ($\alpha = z/t$: where t is the plate thickness).

(3) Using the obtained contribution functions $F_x(\alpha)$ and $F_y(\alpha)$, the equivalent electrical conductivities C_x and C_y are calculated as follows

$$C_x = \frac{\int_0^t F_x(\alpha) \sigma_x d\alpha}{\int_0^t F_x(\alpha) d\alpha}, \quad C_y = \frac{\int_0^t F_y(\alpha) \sigma_y d\alpha}{\int_0^t F_y(\alpha) d\alpha} \quad (8)$$

(4) When the obtained equivalent electrical conductivities C_x and C_y are different from the previously calculated C_x and C_y , and above a certain allowable limit, the electric potential difference is recalculated. When C_x has a small difference relative to its allowable limit, the iteration is terminated and C_x is assumed to be equivalent to the electrical conductance.

Using the equivalent conductivities C_x and C_y , the electric potential function of the laminated plate is obtained.

2.4 New analysis method for a laminated plate including angle plies

Let us consider a case in which the fiber direction is rotated by θ from the x -axis as shown in Figure 4. The electric current can be calculated as follows,

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_x \\ i_y \\ i_z \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} & \sigma_{xy} & 0 \\ \sigma_{xy} & \sigma_{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_t \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{xx} &= \sigma_0 \cos^2 \theta + \sigma_{90} \sin^2 \theta \\ \sigma_{xy} &= (\sigma_0 - \sigma_{90}) \sin \theta \cos \theta \\ \sigma_{yy} &= \sigma_0 \sin^2 \theta + \sigma_{90} \cos^2 \theta \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

When $\theta = 0^\circ$ or $\theta = 90^\circ$, σ_{xy} in the equation (10) becomes zero. For the angle plies, σ_{xy} is non-zero. A non-zero σ_{xy} transforms the equation for the continuity of electric current into a non-Laplace equation. The non-Laplace equation means that the orthotropic electric potential function cannot be applied when the angle plies are included in the laminated CFRP plate. In the present study, therefore, a new approximation method is proposed.

To prevent bending-twisting coupling, angle plies are usually placed adjacent. For example, 45° and -45° -plies are placed adjacent in most real laminated CFRP plates. Even when another ply such as a 90° -ply is included, the 90° -ply is sandwiched between the 45° -ply and -45° -ply to prevent bending-twisting coupling. In the present study, two cases are considered: first, where 45° and -45° -plies are adjacent, and the second, where the layers are arranged in the order 45° -ply, 90° -ply and -45° -ply. Placement of a 0° -ply instead of a 90° -ply, can be considered by replacing the 90° -ply with the 0° -ply.

When a 45° -ply and -45° -ply are adjacent, the two layers can be coupled and assumed to be a ply of double thickness ($\pm 45^\circ$ -ply) as shown in Figure 5(a). The coupling of the plies makes the overall value of $\sigma_{xy} = 0$, from equation (9). This means that the double thickness $\pm 45^\circ$ -ply can be treated as an orthotropic ply of conductivity of $(\sigma_0 + \sigma_{90})/2$. The orthotropic potential function can then be obtained using the equivalent conductivity analysis shown in section 2.2. The equivalent conductivity of the laminated CFRP enables us to calculate the electric potential difference, and the electrical current density for each angle ply using

equation (9). For example, the 45°-ply has σ_{xy} of $(\sigma_0 - \sigma_{90})/2$. The coupling of the $\pm 45^\circ$ -plies used in the electric potential function is a smooth continuous function and the function of 45°-ply or -45°-ply can be approximated by $\pm 45^\circ$ -ply.

When a 90°-ply is located between the $\pm 45^\circ$ -plies, the three plies (45°-ply, 90°-ply and -45°-ply) couple to other cases of $\pm 45^\circ$ -plies. The thickness of the coupled ply is three times that of a normal ply, as shown in Figure 5 (b). The triple-ply coupling makes σ_{xy} zero. This coupling also enables us to calculate the orthotropic electric potential function for a laminate that includes angle plies. The triple thickness ply has $\sigma_x = (\sigma_0 + 2\sigma_{90})/3$ and $\sigma_y = (2\sigma_0 + \sigma_{90})/3$. This enables us to calculate the equivalent conductivity. The equivalent conductivity gives the electric potential function, and the electric current density can be obtained using equation (9).

3. Comparison with computational results

The electric current density results of three types of laminates were calculated using the new method and compared with computational results obtained using FDM to confirm the performance of the new method. The laminated CFRP plate model is shown in Figure 6. The dimensions of the plate were 40 mm \times 40 mm \times 1 mm. For analysis of the electrical current, only the ratio of electric conductivity is important. The electric conductivities in the analysis, therefore, are $\sigma_0 = 1$, $\sigma_{90} = 0.1$ and $\sigma_t = 0.01$. An electric current is applied to an electrode with an area of 0.8 \times 0.8 mm². A grounding electrode also had a similar area. The spacing between the electrodes was set to 20 mm. The applied electric current I was 1000 mA. Three types of laminates were modeled: unidirectional $[0]_T$, $[0/45/-45/90/0]_S$ and $[0/45/90-45/0]_S$.

FDM was used for the computational analysis in the present study. The grid spacing in the x and y direction was set to 0.2 mm and that in the z direction was set to 0.02 mm. The total number of grids was 2,000,000. To check for convergence of computation iterations, the total electric current in the x direction at the cross section of $y = 0$ was compared with the applied

electric current I . For the iteration computations, super parallel computing CUDA ver. 7.0 was performed using a GeForce GTX 970 made by NVIDIA to reduce the computational cost. The total computing time for the analysis was approximately 120 hours. Comparisons were performed at the origin $(x, y) = (0, 0)$ of the plate shown in Figure 6 and at a point A $(x, y) = (-5, 5)$. Because there is no electric current in the y direction at the origin, the electric current density in the x direction was compared with the results of the new analysis at the origin. At point A, the electric currents in the x and y directions were compared with the results of the new analysis.

Figure 7 shows the results of the comparison of i_x of $[0_{10}]_T$ between the FDM and the new analysis. The abscissa is the distance from the surface in the through-thickness direction. The ordinate is the electric current density. The solid curve gives the results of the new analysis and the open square symbols are the results of FDM computations. Figure 7 (a) shows the results at the origin. Figure 7 (b) and (c) show the results of i_x and i_y at point A, respectively. From the total sum of the electric current at the cross section of $y = 0$, the FDM results are approximately 10% higher than the actual applied electric current. This error could be reduced by using smaller grid spacing than that used here; however, this would cause a considerable increase in computational cost, even using GPGPU super parallel computing. Nevertheless the results of the new analysis method appear to agree well with the results of FDM.

Figures 8 (a), (b) and (c) show the results from $[0/45/-45/90/0]_S$. In this case, $\pm 45^\circ$ -plies are coupled into a ply that has double-thickness $\pm 45^\circ$ -ply. The results of the new analysis show good agreement with the results of FDM, and the coupling of $\pm 45^\circ$ -plies into a $\pm 45^\circ$ -ply of double-thickness gives a good approximation of electric current density.

Figures 9 (a), (b) and (c) show the results of $[0/45/90/-45/0]_S$. In this case, 45° -, 90° - and -45° -plies are combined and the electric current density results were calculated using the new method and compared with the computational results obtained using FDM. The results of the

new analysis give good agreement with the results of FDM. This indicates that the approximation of the coupling of three plies, including angle plies, into one orthotropic ply is effective for the analysis of electric current density.

4. Comparison with experimental results

4.1 Experimental method

To confirm the electric current distribution experimentally, three types of CFRP laminates were prepared: $[0_{10}]_T$, $[0/45/-45/90/0]_S$ and $[0/45/90/-45/0]_S$. The material used was IMS60/133 (Toho Tenax Co, Ltd, Tokyo Japan). The laminated plate was cured at 185°C for 2 h at 0.8 MPa. The plate dimensions were 200 mm × 180 mm. The configuration of the CFRP plate is shown in Figure 10.

To measure the electrical current, noncontact current Hall-effect sensors DCZCT-110S (Multi measuring instruments Co, Ltd, Tokyo Japan) were used. To use the sensors, four 15-mm square holes were made, as shown in Figure 10, using machine tools to create five sections, A, B, C, D and E. The sensor measured electric current flowing inside the sensor loop.

Because the electric current does not flow inside the square holes, the measured electric current is slightly different from that of an intact plate, and the electric current flows around the holes. However, because the electric current at positions away from the holes is almost equal to that of the intact plate, the total electric current measured between the square-hall-center locations is almost the same as that calculated by the new analysis method.

To apply the electric current, the electrodes were made using the same method reported in the reference [24] using a copper plating method. An electric current of 50 mA was applied to the plate using a stable direct current power supply PW18-1.3 AT (Kenwood, Tokyo Japan).

4.2 Measurements of electric conductivities

To compare the results of the measurement with the new analysis method, the electric conductivity of each laminate layer should be determined. The electric conductivities in the fiber direction σ_0 , transverse direction σ_{90} and through-thickness direction σ_t were measured using the specimens shown in Figure 11. Electrical conductivity was measured with an LCR meter (LCR Hitester 3522: Hioki E. E. Corporation, Tokyo, Japan) using direct current [22].

Because σ_t depends strongly on the fiber contact between the plies, its value has a wide range and is different for each ply, as described in reference [25]. The electric conductivities in the fiber and transverse directions are measured from the unidirectional laminate $[0_{10}]_T$. The electric conductivity in the through-thickness direction of each laminate was measured using specimens made from each laminate. The total number of specimens for σ_0 and σ_{90} was three, and that of σ_t was five. Electrical conductivity was measured by an LCR meter (LCR Hitester 3522: Hioki E. E. Corporation, Tokyo, Japan) using direct current. The measured results are shown in Table 1. The mean values were used as the material properties of the laminates.

4.3 Comparison of electric current

The measured electric current of $[0_{10}]_T$ is shown in Figure 12. The abscissa is of line section locations (A, B, C, D and E), as shown in Figure 10. The ordinate is the measured electric current at each line section. Open circle symbols denote the results of the new analysis and solid square symbols show the measured results. The results of the new analysis agree well with the measured results as shown in Figure 12. This indicates that the effect of the holes is negligible for the electric current in the line section.

Figure 13 shows the results from $[0/45/-45/90/0]_S$ and Figure 14 shows those from $[0/45/90/-45/0]_S$. In both figures, the calculated and measured electric current values agree

well except for the center. The difference may come from the scatter of the electric conductivity. The conductivity in the through-thickness direction may be different in the each interlamina, and the averaged conductivity depends on the stacking sequences [22]. The difference at the center may come from the This indicates that the coupling approach used in the new method is effective for analyzing the electric current in laminates that include angle plies. At the point C in Figure 13, there is relatively large difference between the calculated and measured results. However, this difference is likely caused by a large local variation of σ_t or fiber miss-alignment of the 0° -ply on the surface of the specimen.

5. Conclusions

A new analysis method is proposed to calculate the electric current of a laminated CFRP plates that contain angle plies. To confirm the effectiveness of the new method, calculated results are compared with other computational and experimental results. The following results were obtained.

- (1) A new method that couples two angle plies, or three plies including angle plies, to obtain an orthotropic electric potential function is proposed
- (2) A new method to obtain equivalent conductivities in two directions is proposed. The coupled ply is assumed to have orthotropic conductivity in the calculation of the equivalent conductivity.
- (3) The results of the new analysis method are compared with those from FDM computations using laminates that contain 45° and -45° -ply. The comparison reveals that the new analysis method is effective for determining properties of laminates including angle plies.
- (4) The results of the new analysis are compared with experimental results further demonstrating the effectiveness of the new method.

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Appendix

Complete formula for the orthotropic electric potential function ϕ in the equation (7) is given as follows;

$$\begin{aligned}
 \phi = & \frac{I}{2\pi(a_{1x2} - a_{1x1})(a_{1y2} - a_{1y1})\sqrt{\sigma_z}} \left[-\frac{y - a_{1y2}}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}} \ln \sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{1x2})^2 + (y - a_{1y2})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}} - \frac{x - a_{1x2}}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}} \ln \sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{1x2})^2 + (y - a_{1y1})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}} - \frac{x - a_{1x1}}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}} \ln \sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{1x1})^2 + (y - a_{1y2})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}} - \frac{y - a_{1y1}}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}} \ln \sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{1x1})^2 + (y - a_{1y1})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}} \right. \\
 & - \frac{x - a_{1x2}}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}} \ln \sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{1x2})^2 + (y - a_{1y2})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}} - \frac{y - a_{1y2}}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}} \ln \sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{1x1})^2 + (y - a_{1y2})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}} + \frac{x - a_{1x1}}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}} \ln \sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{1x1})^2 + (y - a_{1y2})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}} - \frac{y - a_{1y1}}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}} \ln \sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{1x1})^2 + (y - a_{1y1})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}} \\
 & - \frac{z}{\sqrt{\sigma_z}} \left[\tan^{-1} \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_z}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}}}{\sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{1x2})^2 + (y - a_{1y2})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}}} \frac{(x - a_{1x2})(y - a_{1y2})}{z} - \tan^{-1} \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_z}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}}}{\sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{1x2})^2 + (y - a_{1y1})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}}} \frac{(x - a_{1x2})(y - a_{1y1})}{z} \right. \\
 & \left. \left. - \tan^{-1} \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_z}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}}}{\sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{1x1})^2 + (y - a_{1y2})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}}} \frac{(x - a_{1x1})(y - a_{1y2})}{z} + \tan^{-1} \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_z}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}}}{\sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{1x1})^2 + (y - a_{1y1})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}}} \frac{(x - a_{1x1})(y - a_{1y1})}{z} \right] \right] \\
 & + \frac{I}{2\pi(a_{2x2} - a_{2x1})(a_{2y2} - a_{2y1})\sqrt{\sigma_z}} \left[-\frac{y - a_{2y2}}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}} \ln \sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{2x2})^2 + (y - a_{2y2})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}} - \frac{x - a_{2x2}}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}} \ln \sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{2x2})^2 + (y - a_{2y1})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}} - \frac{x - a_{2x1}}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}} \ln \sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{2x1})^2 + (y - a_{2y2})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}} - \frac{y - a_{2y1}}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}} \ln \sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{2x1})^2 + (y - a_{2y1})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}} \right. \\
 & - \frac{x - a_{2x2}}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}} \ln \sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{2x2})^2 + (y - a_{2y2})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}} - \frac{y - a_{2y2}}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}} \ln \sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{2x1})^2 + (y - a_{2y2})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}} + \frac{x - a_{2x1}}{\sqrt{\sigma_x}} \ln \sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{2x1})^2 + (y - a_{2y2})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}} - \frac{y - a_{2y1}}{\sqrt{\sigma_y}} \ln \sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{2x1})^2 + (y - a_{2y1})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}} \\
 & - \frac{z}{\sqrt{\sigma_z}} \left[\tan^{-1} \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_z}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}}}{\sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{2x2})^2 + (y - a_{2y2})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}}} \frac{(x - a_{2x2})(y - a_{2y2})}{z} - \tan^{-1} \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_z}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}}}{\sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{2x2})^2 + (y - a_{2y1})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}}} \frac{(x - a_{2x2})(y - a_{2y1})}{z} \right. \\
 & \left. \left. - \tan^{-1} \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_z}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}}}{\sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{2x1})^2 + (y - a_{2y2})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}}} \frac{(x - a_{2x1})(y - a_{2y2})}{z} + \tan^{-1} \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_z}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}}}{\sqrt{\frac{(x - a_{2x1})^2 + (y - a_{2y1})^2 + \frac{z^2}{\sigma_z}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}}} \frac{(x - a_{2x1})(y - a_{2y1})}{z} \right] \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

Figures

Fig.1 CFRP plate with two dot-type electrodes

General view

Top view with dimensions

Fig.2 CFRP plate with two square-type electrodes

Fig.3 Schematic representation of mirror images used for calculations of electric current

Fig.4 Definition of fiber rotation angle and x-y coordinates.

(a) Coupling of angle plies.

(b) Coupling of angle plies with other ply

Fig.5 Schematic representation of coupled laminates used to calculate equivalent conductivity.

Fig.6 Configuration of a CFRP plate used for analysis.

(a) Electric current density i_x at the origin.

(b) Electric current density i_x at location A.

(c) Electric current density i_y at location A.

Fig.7 Comparison of results from analysis and FDM computations for the laminate $[0_{10}]_T$.

(a) Electric current density i_x at the origin.

(b) Electric current density i_x at location A.

(c) Electric current density i_y at location A.

Fig.8 Comparison of results from analysis and FDM computations for the laminate $[0/45/-45/90/0]_s$.

(a) Electric current density i_x at the origin.

(b) Electric current density i_x at location A.

(c) Electric current density i_y at location A.

Fig.9 Comparison of results from analysis and FDM computations for the laminate $[0/45/90/-45/90]_s$.

Fig.10 Configuration of the specimen used to measure electric current.

Fig.11 Specimen configurations used to measure electric conductivity of CFRP.

Fig.12 Comparison of measured electric current with analysis results of $[0]_{10}$.

Fig.13 Comparison of measured electric current with analysis results of $[0/45/-45/90/0]_s$.

Fig.14 Comparison of measured electric current with analysis results of $[0/45/90/-45/90]_s$

Tables

Table 1 Measured electric conductance of IMS60/133.

	Fiber direction	Transverse direction	Thickness direction σ_t		
	σ_0	σ_{90}	$[0]_{10}$	$[0/45/-45/90/0]_s$	$[0/45/90/-45/0]_s$
Mean value [S/m]	5.91×10^4	6.32	2.54×10^{-2}	1.03×10^{-1}	2.35×10^{-1}
Standard deviation [S/m]	3.58×10^3	2.23×10^{-1}	2.57×10^{-2}	4.66×10^{-2}	1.59×10^{-1}
Coefficient of variation	6.04×10^{-2}	3.54×10^{-2}	1.01	4.52×10^{-1}	6.78×10^{-1}